

Neural Cryptanalysis of Lightweight Block Ciphers Using Residual MLPs

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Abstract—The security of Internet of Things (IoT) devices is a growing concern, given their widespread deployment in environments with limited computational and energy resources. Lightweight block ciphers, such as SIMON and SPECK, are designed to provide efficient cryptographic operations while minimizing computational overhead. However, evaluating their resilience against emerging attack vectors is vital for maintaining robust protection. This paper introduces a neural cryptanalysis approach for evaluating the security of SIMON and SPECK block ciphers, by leveraging a Residual Multi-Layer Perceptron (ResMLP) model in order to approximate the encryption and decryption processes. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach in revealing vulnerabilities, showcasing its efficiency and scalability in performing neural cryptanalysis on lightweight block ciphers.

Index Terms—cryptanalysis, deep learning, lightweight block ciphers, SPECK, SIMON

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) domain offers a plethora of opportunities for driving technological advancement and enabling innovative solutions that shape new paradigms in hardware, software, networking and communications [1]. These developments collectively contribute to the realization of highly interconnected and digitalized ecosystems, laying the foundation for future smart cities [2]. Despite its potential, the IoT landscape faces significant challenges, with security and privacy emerging as primary concerns. Ensuring the integrity, availability, and confidentiality of both devices and data remains a critical barrier, hindering the widespread adoption and trustworthiness of IoT systems.

Cryptography plays a crucial role in mitigating the security and privacy risks inherent in IoT systems. The IoT ecosystem is particularly vulnerable due to factors such as weak authentication, insufficient encryption, and software vulnerabilities, which expose devices to unauthorized access and data breaches [3]. Lightweight cryptographic algorithms [4] are fundamental to address the aforementioned challenges, as they provide security guarantees while minimizing computational overhead, making them ideal for resource-constrained IoT devices. Among these algorithms, the SIMON and SPECK block ciphers [5] stand out for their performance, characterized by low memory footprint and energy-efficient operations. As these cryptographic solutions become integral to securing IoT communications, it is crucial to rigorously evaluate their resilience against emerging threats to maintain the security and reliability of IoT systems.

Cryptanalysis constitutes a key method in this evaluation process. Traditional cryptanalytic techniques, such as linear [6] and differential [7] cryptanalysis, rely on exhaustive mathematical methods that require full knowledge of the cipher's internal structure. These approaches are characterized by high time complexity and significant data complexity, making them computationally prohibitive for large-scale cryptanalysis.

Recent advancements in deep learning have significantly impacted various fields within Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), including cryptanalysis. This has led to the rise of neural cryptanalysis [8], a data-driven approach that leverages neural networks to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of cryptographic ciphers. Unlike traditional methods, neural cryptanalysis does not require full knowledge

of the cipher algorithm and typically operates with lower time and data complexity. By efficiently identifying patterns and potential vulnerabilities, it offers a promising alternative to conventional cryptanalytic techniques, introducing more scalable approaches for security assessment.

In this paper, we propose a neural cryptanalysis approach using a Residual Multi-Layer Perceptron (ResMLP) architecture. This method is specifically designed to analyze the security of SIMON and SPECK ciphers by employing two distinct types of attacks: the Encryption Emulation (EE) Attack which predicts the ciphertext given a plaintext, and the Plaintext Recovery (PR) Attack, which retrieves the plaintext from a given ciphertext. The objective is to train robust ResMLP models that can effectively approximate the encryption-decryption mechanisms of both ciphers. This work demonstrates the potential of neural networks in evaluating the security of lightweight encryption algorithms, contributing to more efficient and scalable cryptanalysis techniques.

The structure of this paper unfolds as follows: This section serves as an Introduction, followed by the presentation of the Related work in Section II. Section III delineates and thoroughly analyzes the concrete steps of our methodology. Section IV engages in a comprehensive description of the experimental setup, followed by the presentation of the associated experimental results and the corresponding remarks in Section V. Finally, in Section VII we consolidate key findings and present concluding remarks, while also outline potential avenues for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

Symmetric encryption is a widely used method for securing data, employing a single key for both encryption and decryption. This approach is efficient for high-throughput data encryption due to its lower computational overhead compared to asymmetric encryption [9]. Symmetric encryption algorithms are generally classified into two main categories:

- **Block ciphers**, such as AES [10], operate by encrypting data in fixed-length blocks of bits, making them suitable for various encryption modes [11] such as Electronic Codebook (ECB) or Cipher Block Chaining (CBC).
- **Stream ciphers**, such as RC4 [12], encrypt data as a continuous sequence of bits, typically offering lower latency but requiring more robust key management compared to block ciphers.

Among block ciphers, SIMON and SPECK are notable lightweight encryption algorithms designed by the National Security Agency (NSA) ¹ for resource-constrained devices. SIMON, optimized for hardware implementations, is ideal for embedded systems and IoT devices due to its Feistel structure and efficient logical operations. In contrast, SPECK, optimized for software, offers higher performance in software-based applications, benefiting from its streamlined ARX-based substitution-permutation design. The main characteristics of SIMON and SPECK are summarized in Table I.

¹<https://www.nsa.gov>

TABLE I: Taxonomy of SIMON and SPECK. Block and Key size refers to the number of bits that the ciphers operate on.

Cipher	Block size	Key size	Number of rounds	Optimization Target
SIMON	32, 48, 64, 96, 128	64-256	32-72	Hardware efficiency
SPECK	32, 48, 64, 96, 128	64-256	22-34	Software efficiency

The structure of lightweight block ciphers, such as SIMON and SPECK, presents unique opportunities for neural cryptanalysis. The iterative round functions and bitwise operations in these ciphers give rise to patterns that neural networks can potentially exploit in order to learn underlying relationships, even in the absence of explicit analytical models. Recent studies [13] have demonstrated that deep learning models can effectively distinguish ciphertexts from random data and predict partial key bits in reduced-round versions of similar ciphers. The following part reviews these advancements, emphasizing techniques relevant to our experimental framework for performing neural cryptanalysis of lightweight block ciphers.

Neural cryptanalysis has gained significant attention in recent years, exemplified by works such as [14], which characterize the phenomenon and provide a taxonomy of cryptanalysis attacks along with associated evaluation metrics. The study in [15] demonstrates the deployment of neural distinguishers i.e. neural networks that are trained for differential cryptanalysis, to deploy them in a PR attack scenario targeting the AES block cipher.

However, the neural cryptanalysis domain gained momentum with Gohr’s breakthrough work presented in [16]. This research explores the application of deep residual neural networks to improve differential cryptanalysis of the lightweight block cipher SPECK. By introducing neural distinguishers that outperform classical methods and developing a highly selective key search policy, it achieves significant improvements in breaking round-reduced SPECK, with reduced computational complexity compared to prior approaches.

In another notable contribution, Jaewoo So [17] employs a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture to conduct cryptanalysis, targeting lightweight block ciphers including simplified DES, SPECK, and SIMON. More recently, [18] proposes a differential analysis method for attacking the lightweight block cipher KLEIN [19], based on deep learning with a model named DABC. This model utilizes an MLP architecture incorporating Linear and Normalization layers, with ELU [20] chosen as the activation function. The authors of [21] review and analyze the research findings of Gohr’s work [16] and, building on their analysis, propose an improved method.

Furthermore, Key Recovery (KR) attacks on simplified versions of AES, SPECK, and DES [22] using neural networks are studied in [23], while [24] presents a comprehensive evaluation of various encryption algorithms under different attack scenarios. Finally, [25] introduces an end-to-end neural cryptosystem designed for IoT device authentication.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Preliminaries

In general, a neural network (NN) can be defined as a function:

$$f : I \rightarrow O \quad (1)$$

where $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is some input domain with n features and $O \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ an output domain.

A deep neural network (DNN) extends this concept by incorporating multiple layers, forming a nested function representation:

$$f(x; \theta) = f^L(f^{L-1}(\dots f^1(x))) \quad (2)$$

where x is the input, θ represents the network parameters, including the weights W and the biases b . The depth of the network is defined by the total number of layers l , where $l = 1$ corresponds to the input layer and $l = L$ represents the output layer, with all intermediate layers defined as hidden layers. Each layer consists of multiple nodes, denoted as n_l , with the outputs of each layer sequentially propagated to the next layer until the final prediction is obtained by the output layer. During training, the backpropagation algorithm [26] is used to compute the gradients of the loss function and update the model parameters (θ) through optimization algorithms such as Adam [27]. This process occurs iteratively over multiple epochs, where each epoch represents a complete pass through all training samples. The training procedure terminates once the loss function converges or a predefined stopping criterion is satisfied.

For each node (neuron) n_l the following operations take place. Let $x^{(l-1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{l-1}}$ be the output of the layer $l-1$ (the input to the current layer l), $W^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times n_{l-1}}$ be the weight matrix of layer l and $b^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ the bias vector of layer l . Then, the output of the j th node is calculated as:

$$o_j^l = \alpha(z_j^l) \quad (3)$$

where

$$z^{(l)} = W^{(l)}x^{(l-1)} + b^{(l)} \quad (4)$$

represents the affine transformation and $\alpha(\cdot)$ denotes the *activation function* (e.g. sigmoid) which is either non-linear or piece-wise linear and is applied element-wise. A common activation function that is used in the paper is the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function which is defined as $a_{ReLU} = \max(0, z)$.

B. Problem Definition

In a block cipher encryption scheme, a plaintext p is transformed into a ciphertext c using an encryption function E_k , parameterized by a secret key k . Given a randomly generated fixed key k of size s_k bits, the encryption mechanism is defined as:

$$c = E_k(p) \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the decryption process reverses this transformation, retrieving the original plaintext p from a ciphertext c

using a decryption function D_k parameterized by the key k and is defined as follows:

$$p = D_k(c) \quad (6)$$

In this work, our goal is to train neural networks in order to effectively approximate the encryption and decryption mechanisms of the lightweight block ciphers SIMON and SPECK. More specifically, we investigate the robustness and security of round-reduced versions of these ciphers by conducting two types of attacks: the *Encryption Emulation (EE) attack* and the *Plaintext Recovery (PR) attack*.

Definition 1 (Encryption Emulation (EE) attack): The EE attack attempts to approximate the encryption function E_k using a neural network. Given a plaintext p , the objective is to predict the corresponding ciphertext c by learning a function f_θ such that:

$$f_\theta(p) \approx E_k(p) \quad (7)$$

where θ represents the learnable parameters of the neural network.

Definition 2 (Plaintext Recovery (PR) attack): The PR attack attempts to approximate the decryption function D_k using a neural network. Given a ciphertext c the goal is to predict the corresponding plaintext p by learning a function g_θ such that:

$$g_\theta(c) \approx D_k(c) \quad (8)$$

where θ represents the learnable parameters of the neural network.

Ultimately, the goal is to conduct the attacks with minimal error, ensuring that the neural networks accurately approximate the encryption or decryption functions. An error value of zero (0) indicates a perfect approximation, where the learned functions become equivalent to the target cryptographic operations:

$$f_\theta(p) = E_k(p) \quad \text{and} \quad g_\theta(c) = D_k(c).$$

We formulate the problem as a classification task, where the neural network learns to map inputs (x) to their corresponding outputs (y). In the EE attack, plaintext samples are used as input and the neural network predicts the corresponding ciphertext as output. In contrast, in the PR attack, ciphertexts are provided as input, while the neural network is trained to recover the original plaintext as output. In both cases, inputs and outputs are represented as bit vectors, with their size matching the cipher block size.

C. Selection of Model Architecture

Since block-sized bit vectors are commonly utilized as inputs and outputs in EE and PR attacks, as observed in the related literature, transformer-based architectures and attention mechanisms are not suitable for this task. These models are primarily designed for Natural Language Processing (NLP), where input data typically consist of sequences with inherent semantic relationships. Similarly, prevalent neural architectures like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) variants, exhibit

limited efficacy. While 1D CNNs could theoretically process bit vectors, both CNNs and RNNs rely on spatial/temporal locality and sequential patterns. However, cryptographic operations in block ciphers intentionally disrupt these properties by leveraging the avalanche effect [28], which results to encryption algorithms that exhibit pronounced sensitivity to bit alterations. Specifically, even minor bit-level modifications in plaintext lead to significant divergence in the generated ciphertext.

Our empirical evaluation extended to unsupervised learning algorithms, including Variational Auto-Encoders (VAEs). However, these approaches produced suboptimal results despite exhaustive hyper-parameter optimization, with resulting model accuracy approximating random chance. The Supervised Auto-Encoder (SAE) [29] architecture showed marginally better performance but failed to meet the benchmarks in related literature. The fundamental limitations lies in these models' inability to construct latent representations that adequately capture the complex input-output relationships of cryptographic functions.

In light of these limitations, we opt for a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)-based architecture, a choice consistent with its extensive use in neural cryptanalysis. Preliminary experiments demonstrated that MLPs outperformed alternative approaches, positioning them as a promising foundation for achieving the objectives of this current work.

D. Proposed Architecture

Our architecture builds upon MLP foundations, improved with residual blocks to enable deeper feature extraction while maintaining stable optimization. By integrating residual connections, we target to address the degradation problem that typically arises with increasing network depth, thereby enabling scalable model depth without sacrificing the network's generalization capabilities.

Blocks. In the context of neural network architectures, a *block* refers to a structured sequence of layers that perform specific operations on the input data. These blocks are often used as modular components to build more complex neural networks. In our proposed architecture, each block consists of:

- **Fully Connected Layer (FC):** This layer conducts the affine transformation, as described in 4.
- **Batch Normalization Layer (BN):** This layer is responsible for stabilizing the training process by normalizing the preceding layer outputs to have zero mean and unit variance, reducing internal covariate shift and improving gradient flow.
- **ReLU Layer:** This is the selected activation function widely used in DNNs, as presented in 3.

The block structure can be represented as:

$$\text{FC} \rightarrow \text{BN} \rightarrow \text{ReLU}$$

Residual Blocks. Residual connections and residual blocks were first introduced in [30] and they reformulate the learning

process by focusing on residual mappings rather direct transformations. In a residual block, the input x is transformed by the block, and the output is added to the original input, forming a residual connection, as depicted in Figure 1. In case there is a mismatch between the dimensions of x and the transformed output, a linear projection W_s is applied to x to align dimensions. This process can be formally defined as:

$$H(x) = F(x; \{W_i\}) + W_s x \quad (9)$$

where $F(x)$ denotes the transformation by the block and $\{W_i\}$ the learnable parameters. The residual block learns a mapping $F(x)$ that represents the difference between the desired output $H(x)$ and the input x , effectively reformulating the problem into learning a residual function $F(x) = H(x) - x$.

Fig. 1: Residual Block

The proposed ResMLP architecture is detailed in Figure 2. The architecture is designed to process and predict bit vectors of 32 bits, which can represent either plaintext or ciphertext depending on the specific attack scenario being considered. The input layer consists of 32 nodes, each corresponding to a feature dimension (bit) in the input data. The core of the ResMLP architecture comprises a series of ten blocks in total. Among those, six are residual blocks that incorporate residual connections, facilitating the network to achieve greater depth for improved feature extraction without compromising optimization stability. Following the sequence of blocks, the network includes a fully connected output layer of 32 nodes. Finally, the output layer is activated by a sigmoid function, which maps the output values in the range $[0, 1]$.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset Generation

Both SIMON and SPECK ciphers were implemented with 32-bit block size, requiring 64-bit keys. The publicly available implementations of these ciphers were extended with custom subclasses that override the rounds parameter, allowing precise control over the number of encryption/decryption rounds instead of default full-round execution. Random 64-bit keys were generated using Python's "random.getrandbits()" method, which was also used for generating the 32-bit plaintexts and ciphertexts.

Two distinct data generation strategies were implemented for each attack type across both ciphers. A unique 64-bit

Fig. 2: The proposed ResMLP architecture. For each block, the number in parenthesis indicates the number of neurons (nodes) in the fully connected layer.

key was randomly generated for each attack instance. For the EE attack, random plaintexts were generated and the corresponding ciphertexts were derived using the respected "encrypt()" cipher method. Conversely, for the PR attack random ciphertexts were generated and the associated plaintexts were recovered using the "decrypt()" method. All generated values were converted from integers to 32-bit vectors and then stored as Numpy arrays, forming the basis for the subsequent neural cryptanalysis.

The dataset size was dynamically scaled relative to cryptographic complexity. For a single round, the dataset size was set to 2^{18} . This increased to 2^{20} samples for two rounds, 2^{22} samples for three rounds and 2^{23} samples for four or more rounds. This scaling reflects the increased data complexity required by neural network models when attacking block ciphers, as additional rounds amplify the diffusion properties of the block ciphers.

B. Evaluation Metrics

In order to evaluate the performance of the trained neural networks in predicting outputs we used the average Bit Accuracy Possibility as defined in [24].

Average Bit Accuracy Possibility (BAP_{avg})

Since the output of the neural network is real number we used the following function to quantize the output:

$$pred_i^n = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } pred_i^n < 0.5 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $pred_i^n$ denotes the predicted i th bit of the n th test sample. The bitwise BAP is then computed over N test samples as:

$$BAP_i = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N XNOR(real_i^n, pred_i^n)}{N} \quad (11)$$

where $real_i^n$ denotes the ground-truth i th bit of the n th test sample. Finally, we average over the block size bs , which in our case is equal to 32:

$$BAP_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{bs} BAP_i}{bs} \quad (12)$$

C. Experimental setup

The experiments were carried out on a dedicated workstation equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 4070 GPU 12GB, an Intel(R) Core i7-14700KF CPU and 64 GB of RAM. The models were built using the Keras framework. The training process utilized the Binary Cross-Entropy loss function and the Adam optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 0.001. Each model was trained for up to 300 epochs with an Early Stopping criterion based on validation loss. Specifically, training was stopping if the validation loss did not improve for at least 0.005 for 15 consecutive epochs. The batch size was set to 128 and the datasets were split into 80% for training, 10% for validation and 10% for testing.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of conducting EE and PR attacks on SIMON32/64 and SPECK32/64 block ciphers using the ResMLP model. We selected 7 rounds for SPECK and 10 rounds for SIMON for both attack scenarios. This choice is based on existing literature, where neural cryptanalysis is typically performed on 1-10 rounds for these ciphers. For each round-reduced variant of both algorithms and for both attack types, the ResMLP model is trained from scratch, resulting in a total of 34 trained models. The key was fixed and randomly generated per attack scenario, leading to four distinct keys used across the experiments.

In several round-reduced configurations, the ResMLP model converged much earlier than the predefined 300 epochs, due to the Early Stopping criterion. This convergence indicates that the model can effectively learn the underlying encryption and decryption patterns faster. Figure 3 demonstrates this behavior by showing the training and validation loss for the PR attack on 3-round version of SIMON. Both losses exhibit a rapid decline until epoch 20, continuing to steadily approach near-zero values by epoch 80. This rapid reduction in loss highlights the ability of the proposed architecture to efficiently approximate the operational characteristics of the block ciphers.

Table II presents the Average Bit Accuracy Probability (BAP_{avg}) for EE and PR attacks on SPECK32/64. The results indicate that the ResMLP model achieves nearly perfect accuracy for both attacks in the first two rounds. However,

Fig. 3: Training & Validation Loss per epoch. Plaintext Recovery attack on SIMON32/64.

for the EE attack, accuracy drops significantly in round 3, with $BAP_{avg} = 0.577$, and approaches random guessing from round 4 onward. In contrast, the PR attack maintains high BAP throughout the first four rounds, only beginning to degrade from round 5 onward. Despite this decline, the PR attack consistently outperforms the EE attack across all rounds, indicating that approximating the decryption mechanism is generally more feasible than replicating encryption.

TABLE II: Average Bit Accuracy Probability (BAP_{avg}) of Encryption Emulation (EE), Plaintext Recovery (PR) attacks using ResMLP model on SPECK block cipher with different numbers of round functions.

Block Cipher	Round Number	EE Attack	PR Attack
SPECK32/64	1	1.0	0.999
	2	0.999	0.999
	3	0.577	0.998
	4	0.508	0.996
	5	0.502	0.845
	6	0.499	0.726
	7	0.499	0.680

The results for SIMON32/64, as shown in Table III, exhibit a slightly different trend. The EE attack remains effective for a larger number of rounds compared to SPECK, with BAP_{avg} staying above 0.88 until round 7 and only dropping to 0.631 by round 10. The PR attack remains highly effective across all rounds, with minimal degradation even at higher rounds. In contrast to SPECK, where PR accuracy declines more sharply, SIMON appears significantly more vulnerable to plaintext recovery. This suggests that SIMON’s diffusion properties are weaker, allowing statistical dependencies between ciphertext and plaintext to persist over more rounds.

TABLE III: Average Bit Accuracy Probability (BAP_{avg}) of Encryption Emulation (EE), Plaintext Recovery (PR) attacks using ResMLP model on SIMON block cipher with different numbers of round functions.

Block Cipher	Round Number	EE Attack	PR Attack
SIMON32/64	1	1.0	1.0
	2	1.0	1.0
	3	0.999	0.999
	4	0.998	0.999
	5	0.922	0.991
	6	0.901	0.988
	7	0.884	0.980
	8	0.790	0.963
	9	0.706	0.959
	10	0.631	0.947

Overall, the results highlight that approximating the encryption process (EE attack) is more challenging than approximating the decryption process (PR attack) for both ciphers. Additionally, SPECK exhibits better diffusion per round, making it more resistant to neural cryptanalysis. This is evident from the rapid decline in BAP_{avg} for both EE and PR attacks beyond the initial rounds. The arithmetic-based structure of SPECK seems to introduce a higher level of complexity, limiting the ability of neural networks to model plaintext-ciphertext relationships effectively. In contrast, SIMON, which relies primarily on logical operations, appears to be more susceptible to attacks based on deep learning.

These findings reinforce the effectiveness of the proposed ResMLP architecture in approximating encryption and decryption mechanisms in lightweight IoT block ciphers. The model’s ability to extract meaningful patterns in SIMON and SPECK demonstrates the potential of neural cryptanalysis in evaluating cipher robustness. The contrasting vulnerabilities between the two ciphers further emphasize the impact of design choices on security, particularly in the context of deep learning-based attacks.

VI. DISCUSSION

The results presented in this work demonstrate that neural cryptanalysis, particularly through Residual Multi-Layer Perceptrons (ResMLPs), can effectively approximate and predict the behavior of round-reduced variants of the SIMON and SPECK block ciphers. This section explores the broader implications of these findings, especially within the context of real-world IoT deployments, where these ciphers are frequently selected due to their lightweight design and minimal energy consumption.

While neural models targeting early-round configurations may not constitute a full cryptographic break under standard assumptions, their predictive power becomes far more consequential in IoT environments, which operate under a unique set of constraints that heighten systemic risk.

First, lightweight block ciphers such as SIMON and SPECK are opted for their low latency and minimal energy footprint, and that is the reason they are usually preferred for applications such as RFID tags, medical implants, smart meters, and embedded industrial sensors. However, this design specifically optimized for efficiency can come at the cost of cryptographic robustness. When such ciphers are deployed in critical IoT systems and infrastructure, the security risks become considerably more severe. A successful attack on these systems could compromise physical processes, enable unauthorized control of critical devices or result in prolonged service outages [31]. Even partial recovery of sensor data may reveal sensitive information, leading to data breaches [32], especially in scenarios where predictable data structures and long-lived keys are used.

Second, IoT data traffic typically exhibits low entropy, consisting of structured and periodic messages such as environmental sensor readings, actuator states or control signals. In such scenarios, even partial recovery or pattern inference can yield meaningful insights for an adversary. High bit accuracy probability in reduced-round configurations, as demonstrated in our results, may enable attackers to infer semantic information from ciphertexts without needing full decryption. Reconstructed control signals, achieved through Plaintext Recovery attacks, could allow malicious actors to inject unauthorized commands or manipulate system behavior, posing significant risks in safety-critical IoT deployments.

Third, the growing capabilities of edge machine learning (ML) hardware are rapidly lowering the barrier for malicious actors to train neural models directly on-device or near the target system using locally captured traffic. While deploying DNNs still demands substantial computational resources, modern edge processors (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson²) are increasingly capable of handling complex ML workloads with relatively low power and memory usage. As this trend continues, malicious actors could realistically exploit side-channel data or unencrypted traffic in situ, turning IoT edge nodes into both vulnerable endpoints and platforms for executing attacks. Consequently, what once required centralized infrastructure and curated datasets may soon become feasible in-the-wild using analogous hardware, especially in poorly defended IoT environments.

In summary, the intersection of architectural constraints inherent to IoT systems, the structural properties of lightweight block ciphers, and the pattern recognition strength of neural network models presents a tangible security risk. These findings emphasize the importance of reassessing cipher configurations in IoT deployments, not solely based on performance metrics, but also considering their susceptibility to emerging

ML-driven attack paradigms. Overall, beyond its value as a cryptanalytic tool for exposing structural weaknesses and guiding cipher design improvements in controlled environments, the proposed methodology also holds significant potential for real-world applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

This work explored the efficiency of ResMLP models in performing neural cryptanalysis on the SPECK and SIMON block ciphers. Our experiments showcased that the models successfully attacked both ciphers, achieving high performance in most cases across Encryption Emulation and Plaintext Recovery attacks. Through evaluating multiple reduced-round configurations, we observed that Plaintext Recovery attacks consistently outperformed Encryption Emulation attacks, with SIMON being generally more vulnerable than SPECK. The results suggest that SPECK's arithmetic-based structure achieves better diffusion per round, making it more resistant to neural cryptanalysis, whereas SIMON's logical operation-based structure retains statistical dependencies for a larger number of rounds.

Future research could include the exploration of additional attack types, such as Key Recovery attacks, in order to access the resilience of lightweight block ciphers under alternative neural cryptanalysis scenarios. Furthermore, experimenting with a broader range of block ciphers, particularly those designed for resource constrained environments, would offer a more extensive evaluation on the effectiveness of the proposed ResMLP model. Finally, future work could explore the role of adversarial machine learning both in optimizing cryptanalytic techniques [33] and in improving the robustness [34] of the developed neural networks. Strengthening these models against adversarial perturbations may increase their effectiveness in analyzing and attacking block ciphers, as well as broader cryptographic mechanisms and protocols.

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